

THE THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE LINGVO-COACHING SYSTEM IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY OF UZBEKISTAN**Juraeva G.B.**

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Annotation. *This article defines the teacher competence in lingua-coaching approach through various characteristics. Furthermore, there are some comparisons between a lingua-coach and a teacher throughout the entire article. Finally, by applying these competences a lingua-coach and a teacher can find the learners' inner motivation and inspiration of using English.*

Keywords: *Teacher Competence, Resistance, Motivation, "Iceberg" Model, Openness, Empathy, Problem Solving.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola turli xususiyatlar orqali lingvo-kouching yondashuvida o'qituvchi kompetentsiyasini belgilaydi. Bundan tashqari, butun maqola davomida lingvo-kouching va o'qituvchi o'rtasida ba'zi taqqoslashlar mavjud. Va nihoyat, ushbu vakolatlarni qo'llash orqali lingvo-kouching va o'qituvchi ingliz tilidan foydalanishning ichki motivatsiyasi va ilhomini topishi mumkin.*

Kalit so'zlar: *o'qituvchi malakasi, qarshilik, motivatsiya, "Aysberg" modeli, ochiqlik, hamdardlik*

Аннотация. *В данной статье компетентность преподавателя в лингво-коучинговом подходе определяется с помощью различных характеристик. Кроме того, на протяжении всей статьи проводятся некоторые сравнения между лингво-коучом и учителем. А также, применяя эти компетенции, лингво-коуч и преподаватель могут найти внутреннюю мотивацию и вдохновение для использования английского языка.*

Ключевые слова: *Компетентность учителя, Сопротивление, Мотивация, модель "Айсберг", Открытость, Эмпатия, Решение проблем.*

Competences emphasize what the instructions have to accomplish during the lessons. The term 'competence' is derived from Latin "competentia" which means the aggregate of the people's personal qualities conditioned by the experience of their activity in a certain social sphere.

Introduction. The first studies on the term "competence" found in Webster's dictionary appeared approximately in 1956 and it is generally understood to mean "the ability to do something successfully and efficiently"[1]. However, the period of its application from theory to practice in education is relatively small. The term "competence" was substituted with the terminology "literacy", which has been used for a long time, although this concept was defined and interpreted in different ways. As a result, the limited understanding of literacy was recognized as a concept that includes only the abilities to read and write. In many cases, literacy began to co-relate with the concept of 'basic skills' comprising listening, speaking, reading, writing, skills in mathematics, working with information, and etc.

It is considered that the term "competence" was initially introduced by R. White in 1959 in the article "Motivation reconsidered: The concept of competence"[2]. Several scholars have attempted various viewpoints to define the term "competence" initially in the field of business. In

accordance with Tracey Weiss, leaders typically struggle ineffectually not because they have technical abilities or knowledge of their job, but rather they have shortcomings in competence.

However, the term came into scientific and practical use from an American linguistics N. Chomsky who introduced the competence in linguistics[3]. Thus, competence in linguistics is “a person’s subconscious knowledge of the rules governing the formation of speech in their first language”[4]. In accordance with the definition of competence in linguistics, we consider competence in lingua-coaching as the formation of forms, techniques, processes, skills and mind-sets that the student is able to acquire throughout **a short-term process**. In the case of higher education it is believed to be a whole academic year. Teacher’s competencies can be adapted through trainings in the classroom or on-the-job experiences. The peculiarity of lingua-coach competences is to deeply engrain the performance that is expected by the leaners.

Literature review. The most well-known author of the book “Working with emotional intelligence” Daniel Goleman’s assumptions seem to be more realistic that “developing competences in social and communicational learning processes nurtured upstream by education system”[5]. Hence, it can be suggested that competence performs in the way which become aware by the others. In lingua-coaching competence indicates how to combine, mobilize and convey knowledge, abilities and skills in a professional context. They can be acquired when there is a communication and an interchange. As a result, the notion of competence should be integrated with the verbs such as how to perform appropriately, how to utilize resources, how to apply responsibilities and duties, how to develop knowledge. Furthermore, the formation process of the competence should assemble value of the lingua-coach.

According to Tracey Weiss, “coaching for competencies is distinctive because it goes beyond helping someone solve an immediate problem. It is making a longer term commitment to the development of that person’s leadership potential”[6]. Although this approach is interesting, however, current solution of Tracey Weiss to coaching competence is disputable in lingua-coaching as it is not a long-term commitment, rather it is a short-term commitment.

It is essential to make a comprehensive analysis of teacher competence through the author of the book “Relational coaching” by E. De Haan. According to him, there are four groups of teacher competences in coaching that can be adapted in lingua-coaching. These are clarifying and making it explicit while being a lingua-coach, using data – based feedback, applying a short-term commitment and choosing an action planning[7].

When we talk about clarifying and making it explicit while being a lingua-coach, teachers are the managers of an educational process and their role is to give directions, set expectations for performance, and eventually, assess the results. However, lingua-coaches made more emphasis on learning rather than on assessing. By focusing on the learners, lingua-coach takes into consideration their both individual and cognitive strategies, which does not characterized the teachers’ competence. Basically, their job is to offer various perspectives and point of views by observing, listening and interfering to raise awareness of issues that the person may have been previously or partly unaware of. Furthermore, a lingua-coach supports the learner with wide range of techniques for all types of leaners, such as auditory, visual and kinesthetic learners, to reflect the given situation. These techniques may include social learning, implicit learning and abundance of information. In this way, the leaners are encouraged to make deliberate choices about altering behavior and about the next steps. Lingua-coach should recognize all the strengths and weaknesses of the learners by self-awareness and openly sharing senses and experiences that are the basement of lingua-coaching competences.

Self-awareness can go beyond the current feeling and reach the aware of lingua-coach's influence on others. In fact, self-awareness is considered as the bridge that can connect the lingua-coach and the learner. The primary role of the lingua-coach is to extend the learners' self-awareness so that it will be possible for them to realistically identify their merits and demerits. This allows the learners to form a repertoire of behavioral reactions to arduous issues in everyday life.

While being a self-aware, it is essential to **open share senses and experiences** straightly with the learner. This is a link to building a relationship with the learner. Unlike a teacher, who gives information and shares with their advice during the lessons or lectures, a lingua-coach always relates his or her reactions and feelings to the learners by being authentic. In accordance with the book "Flawless Consulting" written by Peter Block, being authentic "means that you put into words what you are experiencing with the leader as you work"[8]. Therefore, it is one of the strongest actions that can affect the learner. In a relationship with a coach, the learner is not in the position of the student, but in the position of a partner or a client in exploring their life position, intentions, interests, priorities, goals and plans. At the same time, the learners are prone to reveal themselves when someone is being authentic. When a lingua-coach openly shares his experiences, it assists the learner thinking that a lingua-coach is a genuine who does not have invisible plans. A prosperous lingua-coach manages to persuade the learner that all the recommendations, decisions and assignments are formed on the learner's interests and views rather than his own.

The next moment is using data – based feedback. Feedback is a form of response to the learner's behavior and performance. The aim of the feedback is to enhance the learner's result in the evaluation and learning process. Applying the data is one of the distinctive principles of lingua-coaching that is found in various sources, comprising interviews, surveys, questionnaires and observations. Consequently, listening for comprehension by asking behavioural queries plays a critical role in using data – based feedback.

Methods and materials. Data collection is always driven by the lingua-coach's interviews. Despite the fact that the teacher's lessons usually follow pre-planned route in achieving the result, lingua-coach never prepare beforehand. They accomplish their mission step-by-step in accordance with their learners' interest. By asking pertinent and intriguing questions for particular examples helps the lingua-coach to completely understand the learner's position, his situation, the issues that he encounters in learning the language. It is essential technique as the lingua-coach can extract the learner's ideas and feelings for further feedback in critical situations.

As Linda Nilson interprets, "grading is a task you may view with dread and disdain, but it provides essential feedback to your students on their performance and to you on your teaching"[9]. This seems to be a reliable tip for lingua-coach to carry out systematic relations, with the learners and regulate the grading practice to encourage them.

Taking into consideration *a short-term commitment*, we can assume that the role of a lingua-coach in this process is to be ready to inspect how he or she is able to create and contribute to an arduous situation. If the learner is not sure about the alterations, there is no motivation, and as a result, no learning. Therefore, commitment is vital for alterations in the process of discovery and is a powerful tool that the lingua-coach can assure the learner to trust in themselves while helping them accomplish that their capacity is endless. The lingua-coach, as an instructor, should reflect his confidence in the learner by avoiding the learner's apprehensiveness and creating enthusiasm about on-going possibilities.

Regarding to applying action planning, it is necessary to state that planning gives the lingua-coach an opportunity to predict possible issues while working with the learners and think the ways to cope with them. Most teachers are provided with ready-made syllabus and materials to teach that syllabus. Frequently, it may be in the form of a course book. However, lingua-coach work out individual approach in establishing a definite aim for their sessions. It is essential for the aims to be realistic. For example, if the material is too tough for the student, they may lose their motivation. And vice versa, if the material is too easy, this may cause the boredom of the student. Consequently, it is important to make action planning to a particular learner by critical thinking, problem-solving and motivating.

Conclusion. To conclude, lingua-coaching has been defined as a reflection of a changing relationship between the teacher and the students. It is apparent that lingua-coaching can be the element of the lesson, for example, setting the aim or emerging the crisis situations including frustration or lack of motivation. The competences of a professional lingua-coach listed above can be considered as recommendations for building interaction with students, which entirely fit into the framework of a personality-oriented approach to learning. Moreover, the competences allow for the individualization of the pedagogical and educational process. Hence, lingua-coaching as a pedagogical technology is widely in demand within the framework of individual classes. Teacher competence is critical for successful implementation of lingua-coaching approach. Teachers who possess strong theoretical knowledge of this approach combined with excellent linguistic proficiency, interpersonal skills and reflective practice can create an effective learning environment where learners can develop their communication competence through authentic interaction with others. In addition, the incorporation of lingua-coaching in a group setting can prove advantageous. The lingua-coach can foster group conversations, motivate active involvement, and offer personalized assistance to every learner. This teaching methodology promotes a favorable learning atmosphere where students feel at ease and self-assured in their abilities.

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